

Potentiometric Study of the Quinhydrone Electrode in the Estimation of Nickel.

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Moore (*Chem. News*, 1895, 72, 92) devised a method for the volumetric estimation of nickel salts in solution. The reaction on which the method depended was

To a measured volume of an ammoniacal nickel solution was added an excess of potassium cyanide. The excess of the cyanide was then titrated with silver nitrate solution using potassium iodide as an indicator. On the basis of the method Müller and Lauterbach (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1922, 61, 457) carried on a potentiometric titration. A potential jump against silver electrode was observed as soon as all the nickel was transformed into the complex ion $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_6$. The method did not yield correct results owing to the potential jump being very small at the end-point. An absolute method of the determination of the end-point was then investigated by Müller and Schluttig (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 327) by titrating directly with standard potassium cyanide solution. A potential break was found at a point corresponding to the complex ion formation, $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4$. Owing to the slow transformation of the precipitated nickel cyanide $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$ into potassium nickelocyanide, $\text{K}_2\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4$ there is a great chance of under-titration and the results yielded an error of about 7%. Afterwards they titrated nickel solutions by opposing an inflectional potential of -0.253 volts to that of the cell against normal calomel electrode. An effective stirring and rapid titration was essential in the process of titration.

From the above it is evident that the slow transformation of the precipitated nickel cyanide into the complex salt introduces complications and even in the absolute method of Müller and Schluttig (*loc. cit.*) there is a great chance of over titration giving rise to the positive error. The aim of the following experiments is to locate the end-point correctly at a point when the nickel is completely precipitated as $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$ and the complex salt just begins to form.

The reaction (1) may be represented as (i) the formation of nickel cyanide which being insoluble is precipitated as

$\text{Ni(A)}_2 + 2\text{KCN} = \text{Ni(CN)}_2 + 2\text{KA}$ where A represents an univalent anion;

(ii) the formation of the complex salt $\text{K}_2\text{Ni(CN)}_4$ as

If the end-point can be detected at the completion of the reaction (1), the error due to the slow transformation of Ni(CN)_2 to Ni(CN)_4 will be easily eliminated. The applicability of the quinhydrone electrode will be clear from the following theoretical considerations.

All salts of weak bases and strong acids give an acid reaction. The hydrogen ion concentrations of their solutions is given by,

$$p_{\text{H}} = 7 - \frac{1}{2} p_b - \frac{1}{2} \log C$$

where, C = concentration of the salt, and $p_b = -\log K_b$ and

$$K_b = \frac{(\text{B}^+) \times (\text{OH}^-)}{(\text{BOH})}.$$

The hydrogen ion concentration of nickel salts of mineral acids falls under this class and therefore at the completion of the Ni(CN)_2 formation, the hydrogen ion concentration will be nearly, but not equal to nor greater than, 10^{-7} . (In this consideration, the effect of substances formed during titration has been neglected, although a further consideration will reveal that the effect is not negligible.) When a slight excess of potassium cyanide is added, the complex salt $\text{K}_2\text{Ni(CN)}_4$ is formed and the p_{H} value is given by,

$$p_{\text{H}} = 7 + \frac{1}{2} p_a + \frac{1}{2} \log C.$$

Neglecting C which is very small at the end-point, the change in hydrogen ion concentration is from, $7 - \frac{1}{2} p_b$ to $7 + \frac{1}{2} p_a$. The actual change in *e.m.f.* due to corresponding changes in hydrogen ion concentration will therefore depend upon the values of K_b and K_a as well as on the relative strength of the solutions.*

The abrupt change in *e.m.f.* was seen by a preliminary series of titrations at the point where Ni(CN)_2 was completely precipitated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus.—The apparatus used was of a very simple nature. An accumulator with a variable resistance in series was used along

* Depending upon the variation in hydrogen ion concentration, Rupp and Pfenning (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1910, **34**, 322-323) titrated a neutral solution of nickel with KCN till the point corresponding to the complex ion formation. They used phenolphthalein as an indicator (p_{H} 9.3).

with the ordinary wire bridge potentiometer (made and calibrated by W. G. Pye & Co., Cambridge). The variable resistance was adjusted till a voltmeter placed across the terminals of the potentiometer read exactly one volt. As only changes in *e.m.f.* were to be observed no standard cell was used, although care was taken to see that the current of the secondary cell was constant during the time of the experiment.

Standardisation of potassium cyanide solution.—Potassium cyanide solutions were prepared by dissolving an approximately weighed amount of the salt in a particular volume of distilled water. The solutions were standardised by nickel solutions containing a known amount of nickel in it. The standardisation was necessary in the case of KCN solutions because even the purest sample of KCl available contained sodium salts and moisture.

Estimation of nickel in nickel solutions.—Nickel was estimated by electro-analysis in the solutions meant by standardisation as well as those for titrations in order to determine the percentage of error in each titration. Sand's platinum wire gauze electrodes with rotating cathodes were used. A current of 2 amperes reduced to 1½ amperes towards the end of the analysis was found sufficient to precipitate 0.2 g. of nickel in 30-35 minutes.

Nickel nitrate (which was used for all the titrations) was first converted to nickel sulphate and then made strongly ammoniacal before starting the analysis. In order to prevent the precipitation of nickel in the form of oxide on the cathodes, 2 c. c. of strong ammonia solution was added twice during analysis. The mean of three nearly concurrent readings was taken to represent the actual nickel content. The accuracy of the method and experiments can be judged from the following actual determinations.

		Solution I.	Solution II.
1st determination.	Quantity of Ni per 25 c.c. of soln.	0.1166 g.	0.1444 g.
2nd	do	0.1167	0.1446
3rd	do	0.1150	0.1441
	Mean	<u>0.1161</u>	<u>0.1443</u>

For the purpose of the following titrations pure nickel nitrate (B. D. H., Analytical Reagent) free from cobalt and iron was used. It was intended to study the effect of impurities at a later stage, once the accuracy of the method has been established.

From theoretical considerations it is easy to see that nickel sulphate and nickel chloride would behave in a way similar to nickel nitrate. Some of the results of titrations are as follows.

Solution No. I. Volume of nickel nitrate taken = 25 c.c.

Volume of KCN solution added.	<i>e.m.f.</i> observed against 0.1 N-calomel electrode.	$\frac{dE}{dC}$.	Volume of KCN solution added.	<i>e.m.f.</i> observed against 0.1 N-calomel electrode.	$\frac{dE}{dC}$.
0.0 c.c.	+0.1294 volts.		0.6 c. c.	-0.0924 volts	465
15.0	-0.0489		0.8	-0.1017	400
18.0	-0.0676		20.0	-0.1101	365
19.0	-0.0795		0.2	-0.1174	355
0.2	-0.0823	190	0.4	-0.1245	
0.4	-0.0866	290			

$\frac{dE}{dC}$ maximum at 19.7 c.c. of KCN.

1 c.c. of KCN solution = 0.01738 g. of nickel.*

19.7 c.c. of KCN = 25 c.c. of nickel nitrate solution.

Results.

Amount of nickel in 25 c.c. of solution found by electroanalysis	...	0.3432
do. by titration	...	0.3426
Error	...	0.2

The results of the above and four other experiments are summarised below for comparison.

Quantity of Ni in 25 c.c. of Ni solution as found by electro-analysis.	Quantity of Ni in 25 c.c. of Ni solution as found by titration	Errors.
1. 0.3432 g.	0.3439 g.	-0.1 %
2. 0.8055	0.8066	+0.3
3. 0.1451	0.1441	-0.6
4. 0.1792	0.1791	-0.06
5. 0.0900	0.08952	-0.6

* As found by standardisation by a previous titration

Titration of nickel nitrate solution with caustic soda.

(Use of Quinhydrone electrode).

Volume of nickel nitrate taken = 25 c.c.

Vol. of NaOH soln. added.	<i>e.m.f.</i> observed against 0.1 <i>N.</i> calomel electrode + 1.013.	$\frac{dE}{dC}$.	Vol of NaOH soln. added.	<i>e.m.f.</i> observed against 0.1 <i>N.</i> calomel electrode + 1.033.	$\frac{dE}{dC}$.
0.0 c.c.	+0.0944 volts		21.0 c.c	-0.1058 volts	467
5.0	-0.0278		22.0	-0.1525	771
10.0	-0.0465		23.0	-0.2296	628
15.0	-0.0605		24.0	-0.2924	414
20.0	-0.0920	138	25.0	-0.3338	

$\frac{dE}{dC}$ maximum at 21.7 c.c. of NaOH solution. Strength of NaOH soln. = 0.98*N.*

Results.—Nickel precipitated at end-point is 80%. Hence a basic complex is formed having the probable composition, $\{\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2\}_4\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

In all the above tables only the final titrations are given. Each titration has been repeated several times to test the concurrency of the method.

From the results, *i.e.*, the nature of titration and maxima it is evident that the titration is similar to that of a weak acid with strong alkali and the end-point lies between p_{H} 7 and p_{H} 8.

The above principle was also applied in the titration of nickel salts with caustic soda but the sudden rise in p_{H} beyond 8, when about 80% of the nickel has been precipitated as hydroxide, prevented us from following it further. The sudden change in the direction of the curve points to the formation of some basic compound with nickel nitrate. This was also observed by Britton with nickel chloride (Britton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, p. 2110). Our results point, however, to the formation of the complex salts, $\{\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2\}_4\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

CONCLUSION.

The results of the potentiometric titration (using a quinhydrone electrode) of pure nickel salt (nickel nitrate) with KCN point to a sudden change in *e.m.f.* at a point corresponding to the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$. This change is characteristic of weak acids and can be utilised to titrate nickel successfully. The end-point lies between p_H 7 and p_H 8, which is the case in the titration of weak acids against strong alkalis. It is not possible to titrate nickel by caustic soda because a basic compound is precipitated when about 80% of the nickel has been precipitated as hydroxide.

This method of estimating nickel has the following advantages: In the first place, it does not require any absolute measurements. Only changes in *e.m.f.* during titration need be noted. In the second place, it has the advantage of the titration being finished quickly. The apparatus is also simple and does not require any special care. In fairly concentrated solutions *i.e.*, in solutions containing 0.34 to 0.17 g. of Ni in 25 c.c. of the solution, there is no chance of missing the end-point and the errors are well within experimental magnitudes.

The following are the best conditions under which the above method yields good results.

1. *The concentration* of the nickel solution should be moderate (0.34 to 0.09 g./25 c.c.) As the solution becomes more and more dilute it takes a longer time for the potential to be attained and hence a longer time to finish the titration. Also the changes in *e.m.f.* per unit volume of titer added are small and hence a sharp maximum of (dE/dC) is not obtained.

2. *Stirring.* No stirring device is necessary. As soon as the titer is added into the beaker, it is sufficiently shaken to ensure thorough mixing and then allowed to rest. When the solution is perfectly still, the *e.m.f.* is measured as usual.

3. *The Electrodes.* For quinhydrone electrode moderately thin platinum wires fused in pyrex glass tubes should be used. The platinum wire should not be bent during titration, for a change in the surface strains causes a change in the observed *e.m.f.* When thick wires are used for this purpose the electrodes should be frequently examined to see that no crack exists at the joint and a cracked electrode should be rejected.

The calomel electrode should end in a glass capillary.

4. *The galvanometer.* The galvanometer used should be very sensitive and should give a marked deflection for even very feeble currents, and the lamp and scale method of noting the deflections should be adopted. In the above experiments the author used an Ayrton Mathew galvanometer (Cambridge Instrument Co. Ltd.) and it was quite sensitive. It gave a deflection of 475 mm. for 1 micro-ampere when the scale was at a distance of one meter from the galvanometer.

5. *The accumulator* which supplies current to the potentiometer wire should give a perfectly constant current, *i.e.*, the *e.m.f.* should not change during the process of titration. Even a very small change is likely to cause serious error in the observed *e.m.f.* In the above experiments, a hundred (100) amp. hour oxide battery was used when the *e.m.f.* between the two ends was 2.0 volts, for the *e.m.f.* is not steady when above this voltage.

6. A thorough insulation of all the connecting wires is absolutely essential. The above experiments were performed by using a high quality flexible chords (Rubber and Silk insulated).

